

HISTORY OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS TRAINING
PERSONNEL FOR THE PUBLIC SECURITY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article provides information on the formation and development of higher military educational institutions that train personnel for the public security system. It includes analytical materials on the establishment and improvement of the educational activities of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School.

Keywords: public order, public security, higher military educational institution, military personnel, staffing, qualified personnel, police school, officer.

In recent years, within the framework of large-scale reforms in Uzbekistan, special attention has been paid to ensuring public peace and protecting the legitimate interests of citizens, as well as fostering a culture of law obedience and public security. In this regard, the activities of structures responsible for public security have been further improved, and the quality of training competent personnel in this field has been strengthened.

Today, when examining the history of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the University of Public Security, which train professional personnel for maintaining peace, public order, and security in the country, one can see that they have undergone a long and distinguished journey.

The first police schools were established in Ukraine, the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR), and Belarus between 1916 and 1925. Their activities were regulated by the *Regulations on the Training Courses for Police*

Commanders, approved by the RSFSR Internal Affairs People's Commissariat on April 17, 1921.

The police schools of the national republics were modeled after those in the Russian Federation and drew upon their experience. The establishment of mid-level educational institutions for police commanders was prompted by the *All-Union Congress of Police Officers* (March 1922). To implement the Congress's decisions and create a unified system for personnel training across the country, seven police commanders' mid-level schools were founded.

In 1927, the first educational institution in Central Asia for training mid-level police commanders was opened in Samarkand. According to the order issued by the head of the Central Administrative Directorate under the Council of People's Commissars of the Uzbek SSR (October 15, 1927), the duration of study at the school was set at nine months—from November 1, 1927, to August 1, 1928. The curriculum included general education, military training, political studies, and specialized police subjects. The school was tasked with training mid-level police commanders over a five-year period.

A quota was established for student admissions:

- Surkhandarya – 4 candidates,
- Kashkadarya – 4 candidates,
- Bukhara – 6 candidates,
- Khorezm – 4 candidates,
- Samarkand – 6 candidates,
- A total of 50 candidates from 11 regions were admitted [1, 437].

Applicants were required to have basic literacy skills (reading and writing in their native language, basic arithmetic), at least one year of experience in the workers' and peasants' militia, and be between the ages of 22 and 35.

The Samarkand school operated until 1935. A portion of its teaching staff, including I.G. Kamalov, G.M. Arenberg, G. Kunyashboyev, and M.M. Buligin, was later transferred to the Tashkent Police School [1, 438].

In 1932, according to orders № 986/c (May 25, 1932) and № 776/c (August 14, 1932) of the OGPU's Central Asian office, the Kokand Senior Command School was established. Thus, in the 1930s, there were two police schools in Uzbekistan—the Samarkand Mid-Level Command School and the Kokand Senior Command School. Later, after the closure of the Samarkand school, the Kokand school was relocated to Tashkent, where it became the foundation for the Tashkent Special Police Mid-Level School, the successor of the Kokand Police School [1, 439].

During the first two years, graduates of the school took leadership positions in the OGPU and NKVD agencies. For instance, Abdullah Niyazov rose to the rank of Deputy Minister of State Security of the Uzbek SSR, while Mamajon Akhmedov, Orif Isroilbekov, and Nurmat Tukhtayusupov served as heads of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

In 1933, the school was moved to House № 23 on Lakhuti Street in Tashkent. In June 1935, the school admitted its third cohort. Among the 100 students, four had a seven-year education, 47 had three years of schooling, while 49 were self-taught and had recently completed literacy programs. Considering the national composition of the students, training groups were formed in Russian, Uzbek, and a mixed group that included Tajik, Turkmen, and Kyrgyz speakers.

In 1936, the school transitioned to a two-year education system. However, in 1937 and 1938, frequent disruptions occurred in the learning process due to students being engaged in operational activities.

On the eve of World War II, the Tashkent Police School had become a well-established educational institution with a strong teaching staff and firmly established traditions. The 1939 intake of students had their training shortened due to the outbreak of the Second World War [1, 445].

In 1967, the Tashkent Higher Police School was established under the Ministry of Public Order of the former Soviet Union. Major General Tojidin

Azimovich Jalilov was appointed as its first head. In its inaugural academic year, 85 students were admitted, and the training period was set at four years.

In 1971, the first 32 full-time students successfully graduated from the Higher School. The number of students admitted in the following academic year doubled. Meanwhile, the professional development courses were transformed into a faculty, providing annual training for approximately 200 officers. In 1979, under the initiative of Tojidin Jalilov, a Professional Development Faculty was created at the school. Its main goal was to enhance the professional skills of law enforcement personnel and provide retraining programs.

By the mid-1980s, the school had established faculties for full-time and distance learning, professional development, a special faculty for Dari (Persian) language interpreters, and a faculty for fire safety engineering. Later, the fire safety engineering faculty was separated from the school.

The former Soviet Ministry of Internal Affairs' Higher Courses (Military Unit 5375) were granted the status of a Higher Military Command School by a decision of the Soviet government and the Ministry of Internal Affairs' order dated September 22, 1980. The primary mission of these Higher Courses was to train and retrain highly qualified officer personnel for the Republic of Afghanistan.

The educational institution was considered a reserve force under the operational plan of the Minister of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan, designed to ensure public order and security in Tashkent in case of a crisis, as well as to perform other operational service tasks.

The Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School played a significant role in the continuous staffing of the Internal Troops' personnel.

The Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established based on the Higher Courses of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (military unit 5375) following Directive № 1730 of the Council of Ministers of the Soviet Union, dated October 15, 1990. It was originally named the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School of the Internal

Troops of the Soviet Ministry of Internal Affairs. By the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 1992, the school was transferred under the jurisdiction of Uzbekistan and incorporated into the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs [2].

In 1991–1992, due to the departure of 135 officers from the school to their home countries, the leadership and personnel potential of the Internal Troops in Russia and other CIS states were strengthened, while the departure of talented personnel weakened the academic and educational potential of the military school.

For example, the head of the school, Major General Kh.A. Shogenov, was appointed Minister of Internal Affairs of the Kabardino-Balkarian Republic in Russia. Meanwhile, the first deputy head of the school, Colonel (later Major General) V.S. Agoles, became the commander of the Internal Troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Belarus and later the Minister of Internal Affairs of Belarus [3].

Officers who served at the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School later proved that the institution could become a strong foundation for training military specialists and play a key role in the educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan.

Thus, the situation at the school in 1991 clearly reflected the challenges and difficulties in developing military affairs and ensuring national security in Uzbekistan. In August 1991, the first cohort of 321 cadets was admitted. Most of them came from various parts of the Soviet Union, with a significant portion from Uzbekistan.

Additionally, in the same year, 610 military personnel from various units of the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs' troops underwent retraining, and training for Afghan military personnel continued.

A turning point in the school's history came in early 1992. According to the Decree of the President of Uzbekistan dated January 10, 1992, “On the Internal Troops and Educational Institutions of the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs” and

the order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan dated January 20, 1992, the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School was directly subordinated to the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan and renamed the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan [4].

Given the acute shortage of officers in the Internal Troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan, in 1992, at the initiative of the Internal Troops Command, officer training courses were shortened, and a faculty for advanced training, external research, officer training, and retraining was established. The decision to create this faculty played a crucial role in military personnel training. That same year, 82 specialists were trained within the faculty, significantly replenishing the officer ranks of the Internal Troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan.

In the early years of independence, positive developments within the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan created a need for training military personnel in new specializations. As a result, based on the proposals of the Internal Troops Command and the leadership of the penal system, new specializations were introduced at the school, including officer training, tactical command of Internal Troops, and economics and industrial management.

In 1992, 360 cadets were admitted to the first-year course, including 17 young people from CIS countries. However, the trend of staff members moving abroad, particularly to CIS countries, continued. By 1992, only 172 out of the 302 authorized staff positions were filled.

Amid the mass departure of experienced officers and personnel, the head of the school's academic department, Colonel A.B. Sultanov, temporarily served as the acting head of the school from 1992 until March 1993.

Based on the order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 25, 1993, Colonel (later Major General) Sh.N. Niyozov,

who had held the position of Chief of Staff of the Internal Troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan since 1991, was appointed as the head of the educational institution and managed it until 2009 [5, 34-35].

In 1993, 299 cadets were admitted to the first course of the institution. The Faculty of Advanced Training and Retraining conducted two rounds of enrollment, training 149 military personnel from various power structures of the Republic of Uzbekistan in an external study format. In the same year, 259 military personnel were trained under the warrant officer preparation program.

Along with the improvement of the educational process, continuous work was carried out to enhance the combat readiness of the personnel. In March 1994, the combat readiness of the institution was assessed by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, receiving a rating of “good”.

The institution’s personnel were regularly involved in public order maintenance activities in Tashkent. Since April 1993, 800 military personnel from the institution have performed service in accordance with established procedures for this purpose.

In 1994, efforts to improve the structure of the higher military educational institution continued. To enhance the practical orientation of specialists for law enforcement agencies, and in accordance with the directive of the Presidential Administration, the Department of Educational Work, Psychology, and Pedagogy was established.

Later, in April 2017, the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical Educational Institution of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Military-Technical Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan following Presidential Decree № PF-5005 of April 10, 2017, titled “Measures to Radically Improve the Efficiency of Internal Affairs Bodies, Strengthen Their Responsibility in Ensuring Public Order and Protecting Citizens' Rights, Freedoms, and Legal Interests”.

In August 2017, following the establishment of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the need for highly qualified and professional personnel in this field increased. As a result, in November 2017, in accordance with a Presidential Resolution, the Military-Technical Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was transferred under the jurisdiction of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the Presidential Resolution of April 15, 2021, the The University of Public Security was designated as the primary higher military education and research institution responsible for the targeted training of qualified personnel for the public security system [6]. Additionally, professional training programs were established for the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Guard in the fields of public order maintenance, traffic safety, and passport control. Moreover, training in military diplomacy, jurisprudence, economics, engineering and technical fields, educational psychology, and command-tactical activities was introduced for the Armed Forces and other law enforcement agencies. The system also included professional training in security organization and management for state and economic administration bodies with their own security structures.

In conclusion, professional training of personnel for maintaining public order and ensuring public security at higher military and paramilitary educational institutions remains of critical importance. This initiative supports not only the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Guard but also all security structures of the Armed Forces and law enforcement agencies, providing them with highly skilled specialists. Furthermore, this contributes significantly to the education and upbringing of courageous, brave, and patriotic young individuals.

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